

Assessing the attribute accuracy and logical consistency of road data in OpenStreetMap

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OpenStreetMap (OSM) relies on crowdsourced contributions and lacks strict quality control, ensuring data quality has thus become a key area of research [1]. Understanding and addressing these data quality issues can facilitate unlocking OSM's full potential for diverse applications. OSM data quality assessment methods can be divided into two broad categories: extrinsic and intrinsic. Extrinsic quality assessment methods compare OSM data with a reference dataset (e.g., authoritative data sources). This is where most initial research on OSM data quality started from [2-4]. Yet, a reference dataset may not always be available. On this ground, researchers called for attention to intrinsic indicators of OSM data quality [5] and proposed intrinsic data quality measures based on a snapshot of data, data history, and metadata [5-9].

It is crucial to acknowledge that the quality of OSM data is not a one-size-fits-all metric. Rather, it heavily depends on the purpose of the application domain, known as "fitness-for-use" [5,10]. The diverse application potentials introduce dynamic data requirements. Navigation is one of the primary application domains in which OSM plays a pivotal role. Among them, vehicular traffic constitutes a significant portion of road usage and has a substantial impact on urban mobility and infrastructure planning. Additionally, the complexities involved in automotive navigation and traffic systems require a higher level of data accuracy and reliability, making it a compelling starting point for investigating intrinsic road data quality.

In the context of car driving, the attribute accuracy and logical consistency of road data are particularly important [11]. Attribute accuracy refers to the correctness and logical coherence of attributes associated with road features, such as speed limits, road classifications, and turn restrictions [12]. Logical consistency ensures that the road network data follows the correct topological rules, such as proper connectivity of different road classes. The attribute accuracy and logical consistency of OSM road data are essential for traffic planning and supporting navigation applications.

To address the challenges of evaluating OSM data quality for navigation, when a reference dataset is unavailable, this research narrows its focus to the attribute accuracy and logical consistency of OSM road data. Our current work in progress uses the Munich city centre as a case study.

To assess attribute accuracy, we first identify important attributes related to car driving, such as speed limits, number of lanes, and one-way information [13-15]. Then, our method assesses the attribute completeness of each segment as the weighted sum of the value of each attribute divided by the weighted sum of each attribute with its maximum value. The attribute completeness provides us with a first overview of the attribute data. For instance, as of June 30, 2024, the completeness level of the Munich city centre is 67.185%.

In the next step, a set of rules based on country-specific traffic laws is defined, and the relevant attributes are checked against these rules. So far, we have looked into the traffic law in Germany [16] and the aggregated default speed limits on the OSM wiki [17]. We defined rules accordingly for speed limits regarding the “highway” type. To determine whether a road was in an urban or rural area, relevant attributes like “zone:maxspeed”, “source:maxspeed”, “maxspeed:type”, “zone:traffic” were checked. Then the algorithm verified the value of road segments against the rules. When a mismatch occurred, these road segments were identified and considered as inaccurate. The inaccuracy of the speed limit is calculated as the length of road segments with an inaccurate “maxspeed” value divided by the total road length with the “maxspeed” attribute. Our case study in the Munich city centre revealed a low attribute inaccuracy rate of 0.078%. However, some discrepancies were detected, such as residential roads with a speed limit of 60 km/h (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. An example of a detected road segment with inaccurate maxspeed value. It is marked as a residential road while having a maxspeed of 60 km/h.

Regarding logical consistency, a set of rules was defined based on country-specific conventions, and inconsistent cases were detected against these rules. We acknowledge that different regions in the world have different road construction and mapping conventions. So far, we have conducted our case study in Germany, and defined rules for the values of the “highway” tag. These rules include: the connection of different classes of roads should be logically consistent (i.e., a way with a high level of importance in the road network should not be connected directly to a way with a much lower level of importance);

motorways can only be connected to “motorway” or “motorway_link”; a link road should be connected to its corresponding highway. For each inconsistency type, we calculated the inconsistency rate as the length of affected roads divided by the total length. Since we considered the aforementioned inconsistency the same weight, the logical inconsistency was then calculated as the sum. As such, we are flexible in adding new rules to the indicator. For example, regarding the aforementioned type of logical inconsistency, the Munich city centre has rates of 0.916%, 0.106%, and 0.004%, respectively. The overall logical inconsistency rate is 1.026%.

Our work aims to assess OSM road data quality with a focus on car driving. Current work-in-progress proposed indicators to assess attribute accuracy, with a focus on speed limits and methods for estimating the logical consistency of road data. Checking the speed limits and their sources against default speed limits offers an initial assessment to attribute inaccuracy, as the speed limit is one of the most important road attributes related to car driving. It also provides the starting point of a scalable approach to extend to a global scale. Worth noting for attribute inaccuracy is that this indicator assesses the data against the country's default speed limits. In reality, many roads are regulated by traffic signs, with more strict speed limits. If a road segment is not flagged as inaccurate, it does not necessarily mean it is accurate. This indicator shows the road attribute quality, but should not be understood as indicating accuracy. In addition, exceptional cases may exist, for different temporal scales, which should also be treated cautiously.

As an indicator aggregated by individual measures, logical consistency offers varying levels of detail, thus suitable for different levels of decision-making. The logical inconsistency rate presents a high-level overview of the data quality. Users can make informed decisions on whether to use OSM as a data source for specified areas. Once the high-level decision is made, examining the error types and searching for relevant solutions to process data can be the next step. When the inconsistency rate is low and occurs at the individual case level, reviewing the detected cases is more beneficial than focusing on the calculated inconsistency rate.

In the next step, we plan to conduct a user study with navigation service providers, aiming at identifying crucial attributes for routing services tailored to car driving, in order to improve the attribute completeness indicator. In terms of attribute inaccuracy, we plan to scale it up to the global level, by implementing the default speed limits aggregated from contributors on the OSM Wiki [17], as well as using large language models to help verify the aggregated speed limits. As exception cases for speed limits exist in reality, we can consider introducing other tags into the analysis. Another possibility would be leveraging the crowd wisdom further to collect exceptional cases, by potentially collecting such data in the OSM wiki page.

With the proposed assessment, OSM data users can verify road data quality in terms of attribute accuracy and logical consistency, before their intended use. With the evaluation method, we also aim to inform the potential improvement of OSM road data quality, especially for navigation.

References

- [1] Yan, Y., Feng, C., Huang, W., Fan, H., Wang, Y., & Zipf, A. (2020). Volunteered geographic information research in the first decade: a narrative review of selected journal articles in GIScience. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 34(9), 1765–1791.
- [2] Girres, J., & Touya, G. (2010). Quality assessment of the French OpenStreetMap dataset. *Transactions in GIS*, 14(4), 435–459.
- [3] Haklay, M. (2010). How good is volunteered geographical information? A comparative analysis of OpenStreetMap and Ordnance Survey datasets. *Environment and Planning B: Planning and Design*, 37(4), 682–703.
- [4] Zielstra, D., & Zipf, A. (2010). A comparative study of proprietary geodata and volunteered geographic information for Germany. *Proceedings of the 13th AGILE International Conference on Geographic Information Science*, 1–15.
- [5] Barron, C., Neis, P., & Zipf, A. (2014). A comprehensive framework for intrinsic OpenStreetMap quality analysis. *Transactions in GIS*, 18(6), 877–895.
- [6] Fogliaroni, P., D'Antonio, F., & Clementini, E. (2018). Data trustworthiness and user reputation as indicators of VGI quality. *Geo-spatial Information Science*, 21(3), 213–233.
- [7] Nejad, R. G., Abbaspour, R. A., & Chehrehghan, A. (2022). Spatiotemporal VGI contributor reputation system based on implicit evaluation relations. *Geocarto International*, 37(26), 12014–12041.
- [8] Severinsen, J., De Róiste, M., Reitsma, F., & Hartato, E. (2019). VGTrust: measuring trust for volunteered geographic information. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 33(8), 1683–1701.
- [9] Sundaram, R. C., Naghizade, E., Borovica-Gajić, R., & Tomko, M. (2021). Can you fixme? An intrinsic classification of contributor-identified spatial data issues using topic models. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 36(1), 1–30.
- [10] Senaratne, H., Mobasheri, A., Ali, A. L., Capineri, C., & Haklay, M. (2017). A review of volunteered geographic information quality assessment methods. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 31(1), 139–167.
- [11] Wu, H., Lin, A., Clarke, K. C., Shi, W., Cardenas-Tristan, A., & Tu, Z. (2021). A comprehensive quality assessment framework for linear features from Volunteered Geographic Information. *International Journal of Geographical Information Science*, 35(9), 1826–1847.
- [12] Alghanim, A., Jilani, M., Bertolotto, M., & McArdle, G. (2021). Leveraging road characteristics and contributor behaviour for assessing road type quality in OSM. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-information*, 10(7), 436.
- [13] Hiller, J., Müller, F., & Eckstein, L. (2021). Aggregation of Road Characteristics from Online Maps and Evaluation of Datasets. *Proceedings of 2021 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV)*, Nagoya, Japan, 208–214.
- [14] Liu, Y., & Hansen, J. H. (2019). Towards complexity level classification of driving scenarios using environmental information. *Proceedings of 2019 IEEE Intelligent Transportation Systems Conference (ITSC)*, Auckland, New Zealand, 810–815.
- [15] Zheng, Y., Izzat, I. H., & Hansen, J. H. (2019). Exploring OpenStreetMap availability for driving environment understanding. *arXiv preprint*, arXiv:1903.04084.
- [16] Straßenverkehrs-Ordnung (StVO) (2024). Retrieved from https://www.gesetze-im-internet.de/stvo_2013/BJNR036710013.html
- [17] OpenStreetMap Wiki (2024). Default speed limits. Retrieved from https://wiki.openstreetmap.org/wiki/Default_speed_limits